

1 **Xrn1 controls Parp9/14 activation.**

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6 Activation of the enzymes Parp9 and Parp14 is a common transcriptional feature of pathways important
7 for IBD, identified by gene or casual variant of interest, including NOD2, TRIM22, and XIAP.

8 Aberrant Parp9/14 pathway signaling is found in NOD2 mutant cells and in patient tissues of humans with
9 IBD (Crohn's Disease).

10 We used transcriptome profiling together with XRN1 depletion or knockout in human cells to study XRN1
11 nuclease activity modeling Parn and Xrn1 inhibition in IBD.

12 Targeting these nucleases provided an opportunity to study early events in IBD etiology (at the level of the
13 founder cell of origin) and to support targeted management of ensuing interferon activation, global
14 pathway activation associated with Parp9/14 induction.

15 Parp9/14 transcriptomic search identified Xrn1 and Xrn2 as Parp9/14 regulated nucleases. Genes in this
16 network included a significant enrichment of molecules function in T-cell activation (e.g., LST1) as well as
17 another IBD susceptibility locus, TAGAP.

18 We previously demonstrated induction of Parp9/14 resulting from NOD2 mutation found in CD. Consistent
19 with data from reporter cells engineered to express an IBD-associated mutation in NOD2, Parp9
20 expression was significantly reduced in Xrn1 KO cells.

21 We demonstrate here thus control of Xrn1/2 by Parp9. Parp9 and Parp14 reside downstream of Xrn1 and
22 the function it performs in the NOD2-XIAP-TRIM22-XRN1-PARP9/PARP14 signaling pathway.
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